

THE PERSONA OF SEVEN MARKETPLACES AND THE CONSUMERS' PREFERENCES

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Abstract

Numerous varieties of marketplaces exist, each catering to distinct customer segments. Customers tend to gravitate towards specific online marketplaces in favor of rivals, showcasing the alignment between customer preferences and the personas embodied by different online marketplaces. Neuromarketing is a digital marketing strategy that based on neurosciences, in this research to analyses the brand personality or persona of each marketplace. MSMEs, as the majority of players in Indonesia, need support to strengthen the digital ecosystem, by examining the digital persona of the top 7 marketplaces in Indonesia: Blibli, Bukalapak, Lazada, Shopee, TikTok Shop, Tokopedia and Zalora and to identify the consumers' preferences. The personas in this study are based on the motive focus of advertisements perceived by consumers. The research method used is a quantitative survey conducted to explore brands associated with seven marketplaces in Indonesia, as well as to determine the impact of online dimensions on the customer decision-making process. This research uses a non-probability random sampling technique. The data collection method uses snowballing technique with total respondents that meet the criteria are 440 out of 442. The results of this study are that 7 marketplaces in Indonesia have similar values, features, and motives that are in the Limbic Map of the Balance System. As for the Limbic Map, because of the marketplace brand in the Balance System, the limbic type is Harmonizer. The consumers' preferences on online dimensions are Persona, Domain Name, Personalization, Design, and Entertainment.

Keywords: Neuromarketing; Brand Personality/Persona; Digital Marketing; Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs)

INTRODUCTION

In the year 2022, Indonesia's e-commerce transactions ranked third in terms of the highest sales growth (23%) and held the 10th position in terms of total sales volume (USD 58 billion) (eMarketer, 2022). The rise of e-commerce has been boosted by the advancement of the internet. Mobile connectivity data in Indonesia reached 128.0% of the total population (Kemp, 2023). Internet users engaging in weekly online shopping constitute 62.6%, positioning Indonesia as the third highest in the world. However, businesses that conduct transactions within the digital economy account for only 25.92%, according to research by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), indicating that the majority of enterprises in Indonesia have yet to harness the advancements of digital technology (BPS, 2021). Digital Economy, based on

information technology, will offer a broader market scope from the marketing perspective. Business actors need to possess an understanding of customer personas and experiences across different platforms to execute precise digital marketing strategies (Salvietti et al., 2022). There exist numerous types of marketplaces, each having its own customer base. Customers develop preferences for specific online markets over competitors (Kemora & Pasaribu, 2023). This illustrates a congruence between customer preferences and online market personas. Purchase intent is influenced by brand personality or persona (Aaker, 1997; Toldos-Romero & Orozco-Gómez, 2015; Xu et al., 2023), necessitating digital marketing strategies aligned with customer personas and the creation of business personas, also known as neuromarketing.

The advancement of neuromarketing reinforces research and marketing applications within the realms of consumer behavior and brand identity or personality (Arora & Jain, 2021; Wicinski et al., 2022). Micro, Small, and Medium-sized Enterprises (MSMEs), as the majority players in Indonesia, need support for bolstering the digital ecosystem. In the field of neuromarketing research, Hausel develops the limbic mapping and categorization of limbic types to identify the emotions, motives, and personal values relevant to communication strategies (Häusel, 2011; Rüschenndorf, 2020). Mapping brand personality and its customers will yield communication marketing strategies meeting customer expectations, resulting in product purchases, reviews, emoticon likes, and fostering loyalty through repeat purchases (Akter & Sultana, 2020; Delgado-Ballester, 2016; Xu et al., 2023a). This is founded the grand theory of brand-consumer relation i.e. “similarity – attraction” (Aaker, 1997; Xu et al., 2023) On the other hand, the primary causes of failure for novice business actors are attributed to the market (42%), poor marketing (14%), and neglecting customers (14%) (Steward, 2022). This is exacerbated by the low penetration of MSMEs in the digital economy (BPS, 2021), while the potential for the Indonesian e-commerce market is substantial, with 62.6% of internet users engaging in online shopping every week (Kemp, 2023). MSMEs require proper guidance and directions to execute effective and efficient digital marketing, both on marketplace platforms and social media. Based on the aforementioned, this research aims to create a digital brand personality map or known as Persona of seven top marketplace in Indonesia (Blibli, Bukalapak, Lazada, Shopee, Tiktok Shop, Tokopedia and Zalora) perceived by customers and to see the effect of Persona and other brand identity dimension on consumer’s preference on marketplace in Indonesia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Neuromarketing

Neuromarketing is an approach in marketing that utilizes insights from neuroscience to understand consumer behavior and design more effective marketing strategies. This term emerged in 2002 when some American companies began offering research in the field of neuromarketing, rooted in cognitive neuroscience (Morin, 2011). Harrell (2019) states various neuroscience instruments in understanding the consumers’ behavior. Neuromarketing can be regarded as an intersection of marketing, neuroscience, and psychology (Alsharif et al., 2021). The role of neuromarketing is believed to add value to branding, product design, advertising, and media in promotion (Wicinski et al., 2022).

Table 1: Neuroscience Instruments for Digital Marketing

	How neuroscience instrument operates	Utilization
fMRI (functional magnetic resonance imaging)	The detection of blood flow in the brain is closely associated with heightened neural activity.	The establishment of prices and the enhancement of the brand.
EEG (electro-encephalogram)	The process of capturing electrical signals on the scalp originating from neurons within the brain	Enhancing Advertising and Branding
Eye tracking: gaze	Precisely identifying the direction toward which subjects direct their gaze.	Improving the design of websites, advertisements, and packaging
Eye tracking: pupilometry	Quantifying the dilation of the subject's pupils in a scientific context.	Improving the design of websites, advertisements, and packaging
Biometrics	Assessing skin conductance, heart rate, and respiration	Improving effectiveness and quality of advertising content
Facial coding	Analyzing and recognizing facial expressions	Improving effectiveness and quality of advertising content

Source: (Harrell, 2019)

Brand Personality

Brand Personality pertains to a collection of human traits connected with a brand. Research on BP focuses on how it enables consumers to convey their thoughts and feelings or express themselves, embody an ideal version of oneself, or specific dimensions of themselves in using a brand. This serves as a primary method to distinguish a brand, a key driver of consumer preference and usage, and a common denominator for cross-cultural brand marketing (Aaker, 1997). Research into BP in the digital realm commenced in the 2000s. Ghorbani conducted a literature review and found that the framework for BP utilized is the Brand-as-a-person or brand-as-a-personality framework, influenced by various factors and antecedents such as channel type, platform design, and diverse influencing factors like cognitive consequences (brand authenticity, perceived quality) or affective consequences (brand loyalty, customer satisfaction) (Ghorbani et al., 2022).

In the digital context, the term BP is referred to as "Persona," representing a semi-fictional Brand-as-a-person (Cui et al., 2019), while the consumers associated with it are termed "Buyer Personas," signifying individuals who willingly and voluntarily purchase products that are personified (Patrutiu-Baltes, 2016). Kollmann & Suckow (2012) introduced a novel framework that amalgamates the behavioral-based and identity-based approaches. This framework was designed to elucidate the notable brand identity dimensions that play a crucial role in shaping brand attitudes within the realm of E-commerce platforms.

The framework encompasses several facets, including attitude constructs such as dimensions of emotion, cognition and conation. Moreover, the dimensions of online shop were established through a meticulous analysis of content, performed by experts in online branding. This analysis involved the grouping of significant expressions into coherent clusters, each of which was assigned relevant labels. Hausel (2011) formulated a limbic map and limbic type model, capable of discerning the emotions, motivations, and values of an individual, which are

pertinent for the formulation of a focused communication strategy. In the process of crafting such a targeted strategy, the delineation of the target demographic and the synchronization of consumer needs and values assume paramount significance.

Limbic Map

Häusel's (2011) limbic map presents a structure that holds potential for marketers to discern values and emotions that strike a chord with pertinent target audiences. Within this framework, he delineated three principal motivational and emotional systems recognized as the Big 3: the balance system, the stimulant system, and the dominance system (Figure 1). These motivational systems exhibit concurrent activities, thereby leading to their reinforcement through sub-modules embodying amalgamations of the Big 3.

Source (Häusel, 2011)

Figure 1: Limbic Map

Limbic Type

Häusel (2011) identified distinct limbic types that mirror consumer personalities through a blend of various classifications within the Big 3 and their sub-modules. This categorization holds potential for target audience segmentation and analysis, thereby aiding the formulation of a communication strategy. The ensuing Limbic Types are as follows further explained by Rüschenndorf (2020):

Harmonizer: The Balance system is merged including the care and bonding systems. This type places emphasis on modest advancement as well as status orientation, consequently underscoring the significance of family and domesticity. The consumption priorities are directed towards products for the family and home context.

Open-minded: A fusion within the stimulant system and the Balance system. The prevalence of the stimulant system yields a positive outlook or optimistic perspective on life, with a penchant for valuing both established and novel enjoyments and experiences. The influence of the balance system directs attention towards the source and quality of a product.

Hedonist: The prevalence of the stimulant system leads to an ongoing quest for fresh experiences, characterized by a notable level of individualism and spontaneity. Individuals within this category prioritize the uniqueness or distinctiveness and novelty of a product, considering its quality to be of lesser importance.

Adventurer: A prevailing stimulus system combined with a touch of the dominance system. This cohort exhibits a heightened inclination for willingness to take risks and diminished management of impulses. For this segment, consumption revolves around amusement and exhilaration; consequently, products for this group should encapsulate a sense of liberation or performance enhancement.

Performer: The Dominance system holds sway within this category. The persona of this group centers on achieving excellence and harboring ambitious aspirations. When selecting products, their emphasis rests on quality and the pursuit of perfection.

Disciplined: A blend within the dominance system predominance with a touch of the balance system yields a somewhat pessimistic stance or negative viewpoint. The character of this group is marked by a strong sense of responsibility and minimal consumerism, translating to purchasing only what is deemed necessary. In product selection, their focus inclines towards quality, guarantees, and thriftiness.

Traditionalist: The dominance system takes prominence here, signifying the group's cautious and skeptical approach toward novelty. Their personality revolves around order and security, coupled with a limited forward-looking mindset. In the realm of product selection, their attention centers on the brand's reliability and trustworthiness, as they meticulously analyze particulars and exhibit relatively rigid consumer behaviors.

Neuromarketing and Digital Marketing

Premnath formulated a theoretical framework for developing Neuromarketing-based digital marketing applications that lead to brand loyalty (Premnath & Nateson, 2021). Research about the impact of Neuromarketing towards social media marketing as part of digital marketing shows its effects on business communication sustainability and, ultimately, business sustainability (Constantinescu et al., 2019). Utilizing the concept of Brand Personality with the basis of neurosciences in digital marketing, such as in short videos, allows for brand personification that supports emotional alignment of consumers with the brand and helps in the formation of consumer psychological identity (Cui et al., 2019). The Limbic Map and Limbic

Type integration, as a result of Neuromarketing is used to map personas from the online market in Turkey, specifically Trendyol in the Adventure/Sensation Limbic Map with a dominant Adventurer Limbic type (Kemora & Pasaribu, 2023). Consumer engagement in digital marketing is part of inbound marketing strategy, such as through user-generated content and online word-of-mouth communication. (Saura et al., 2020).

Figure 2: Research Framework of Persona and Consumers' Preferences on Brand Identity

HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Persona

Persona is a variable that represents the brand persona based on Hausel's Limbic Mapping and Type of Limbic (Häusel, 2011; Rüschenndorf, 2020). Persona in this research is based on the marketplace focus of advertising perceived by consumers. Digital BP or Persona has consequences towards attitude of customers on cognitive (such as perceived quality), affective (brand loyalty) and conative (purchase intention) (Ghorbani et al., 2022). Furthermore, the mechanism of "similarity-attraction" pertaining to brand personality is present. The brand personality's attraction mechanism towards consumers is robustly underpinned by psychological theories. A significant theory in this context is theory of self-consistency, which posits that customers tend to favor brands possessing personality attributes akin to their own (Xu et al., 2023). Toldos-Romero & Orozco-Gómez (2015) finding showed that there is a positive and significant effect brand personality towards purchase intention.

H_{Persona} : Persona has a positive effect on the attitude of customers.

Consumers' Preference on Brand Identity

Kollman & Suckow (2012) discovered that all dimensions of brand identity significantly influence the attitudes of visitors. Furthermore, it revealed that attributes such as interactivity exert notable yet comparatively modest impacts on attitude. Finding of marketplace in Turkiye shows that interactivity gives significant effect (Kemora & Pasaribu, 2023).

H₁: Interactivity has a positive effect on consumer attitude.

Concerning the formation of attitudes among first-time visitors to online shops, information quality has demonstrated positive high levels of significance (Kollmann & Suckow, 2012). Results shows a different in Turkiye whereas information quality is a negative significant towards attitude (Kemora & Pasaribu, 2023). Furthermore, it should be noted that the dimension of information quality, encompassing both intrinsic and contextual attributes, has also been determined to exert an impact on attitude. This facet of information quality pertains to visitors' perceptions regarding the abundance, caliber, and quantity of information presented within the online shop, alongside the structure and arrangement of said information (Kollmann & Suckow, 2012).

H₂: Information Quality has a positive effect on consumer attitude.

Usability is a subjective perception, as its assessment hinges on an individual's aptitude to maneuver through the website or platform of the online shop. Usability has a significant positive impact on attitude (Kemora & Pasaribu, 2023; Kollmann & Suckow, 2012).

H₃: Usability has a positive effect on consumer attitude.

Research conducted by Kollmann & Suckow (2012) revealed that the design perceived by customers has a positive impact on the comprehensive visual representation of the online shop, consequently influencing brand perception. This sentiment is in line with the observations of Kemora & Pasaribu (2023).

H₄: Design has a positive effect on consumer attitude.

The entertainment dimension encompasses captivating attributes that incite visitors to persist in their exploration of the website. In addition to prolonging the duration of their stay on the site, this dimension enhances the seamless processing of information and triggers sensory reactions. Consequently, it is advisable for online shops to meticulously design their websites to encompass not solely functional facets but also emotional dimensions, thereby fortifying hedonistic principles. Preceding investigations have also corroborated that entertainment bears a favorable impact on users' intentions to revisit a website (Kollmann & Suckow, 2012). However, this finding differs from the research conducted on the Trendyol marketplace in Turkiye (Kemora & Pasaribu, 2023).

H₅: Entertainment has a positive effect on consumer attitude.

Customizing information to heighten the pertinence of content for individual users is referred to as the personalization dimension, which has likewise demonstrated a positive influence on attitude. By delivering tailored content, online shops have the potential to elevate the visitor

experience by addressing their requirements and facilitating task completion. Earlier research has also underscored the repercussions of personalization on loyalty and consumer behavior (Kemora & Pasaribu, 2023; Kollmann & Suckow, 2012)(Mouammine et al., 2019).

H₆: Personalization has a positive effect on consumer attitude.

Kollmann & Suckow (2012) explicates that coherence between the brand name and the domain name enhances brand recognition, thus fortifying the connectivity of message pathways across channels.

H₇: Domain Name has a positive effect on consumer attitude.

METODE PENELITIAN

Research Questions

The fundamental structure of the study involves an amalgamation of consumer attributes rooted in the Limbic Theory of neuromarketing (Häusel, 2011) and the Kollman & Suckow Model (2012), which pertains to influencing user attitudes through effective brand communication in digital marketing in marketplace platforms. The primary research inquiry encompasses the evaluation of seven (7) marketplaces in Indonesia: Blibli, Bukalapak, Lazada, Shopee, TikTok Shop, Tokopedia and Zalora in figuring out their Persona perceived by customers. The secondary inquiry revolves around the dissection of the multi-dimensional including Persona and seven brand identity towards consumer attitudes on marketplace online shopping. In this second phase, it will resolve empirically if Persona matters or customers' limbic types based on neuromarketing as a determinant among the factors influencing consumer attitudes. To address the initial research inquiry (research question #1), which pertains to understanding the persona of marketplaces, a quantitative survey was conducted to explore the brand perceptions associated with seven distinct marketplaces in Indonesia. This methodology closely mirrors a prior investigation conducted by Rüschenndorf (2020), focusing on brand perception and positioning. The study particularly emphasizes the utilization of Hausel's Limbic Map and Limbic Type (2011).

In response to the second research question (#2), "To what extent do the online dimensions of marketplace platforms, along with their brand identity and Persona, influence customers' selection of online marketplaces?" a quantitative survey was executed. This survey methodology replicates the approach introduced by Kollman and Suckow (2012) by adding the variable Persona (as the result of initial inquiry), aimed at quantitatively examining these factors. This selection was made to underscore whether the online dimensions additionally wield an impact on customers' decision-making processes.

Research Instruments

Research Question #1

Instruments developed by (Rüschenndorf, 2020) based on Limbic Map and Limbic Type Hausel Theory was used in answering the first research question. There are three questions to comprehend the Persona of seven marketplaces by brand perception.

1. Which of the following values and terms are most important for your life?

Respondents need to choose five values among 18 values representing the values of Limbic Map of Hausel. This question is answering the Limbic Map of customers on each marketplace.

Table 2: Limbic Map and its Values

Limbic Map	Values
Balance	Family
	Reliability
	Tradition
Fantasy/Pleasure	Pleasure
	Individuality
	Fantasy
Stimulant	Fun
	Humour
	Creativity
Adventure/Thrill	Spontaneity
	Courage
	Risky Appetite
Dominance	Freedom
	Victory
	Ambition
Discipline/Control	Order
	Discipline
	Thriftiness

Source: (Rüschendorf, 2020)

2. How important are the following product features for your buying decisions?

Using Likert scale 1 to 5 for preferences from the least important to the most important. The question is figuring out the Limbic Type of customer in each marketplace.

Table 3: Limbic Type and its Associated Product Feature

Limbic Type	Product Feature
Harmonizer	Family-friendliness
Open-Minded	Quality
Disciplined	Low price
Adventurer	Performance
Performer	Status Symbol/Brand Name
Traditionalist	Habit
Hedonist	Innovation

Source: (Rüschendorf, 2020)

3. To what extent are the following motives in the focus of marketplace's advertisement?

Pleasure / Ease / Cordiality / Friendship / Adventure / Spontaneity / Freedom / Rebellion / Victory / Pride / Reliability / Tradition / Quality

Using Likert scale 1 to 5 for preferences from the least focus to the most focus for each motive. The question is finding out the position of Limbic Map or Persona of marketplace perceived by customers. Variable Persona is derived from indicator in question no.3 that is used for answering research question #2.

Research Question #2

Within this study, a sum of seven distinct independent variables is considered, encompassing the seven dimensions of online shopping. Concurrently, three distinct factors are adopted as dependent variables, drawing from the framework established by Kollman and Suckow (2012) and Kemora & Pasaribu (2023) adopted in Turkiye's marketplace research. Using Likert scale 1-5 from the least important to the most important. By adding the Persona, the total of independent variables is eight (8).

Table 4: Variable of Brand Identity and Consumer Attitude

No.	Variable	No.of Item
1	Persona	13
2	X1: Interactivity	4
3	X2: Information Quality	4
4	X3: Usability	3
5	X4: Design	4
6	X5: Entertainment	3
7	X6: Personalization	4
8	X7: Domain Name	4
9	Y: Attitude	13

Source: Processed Data (2023)

Sampling

The research employs a non-probability random sampling technique, which stands as a method for selecting a sample not contingent upon the principles of probability theory. Consequently, it does not necessitate equal opportunity of population members for selection. The selection of the sample is determined by subjective criteria; however, it is imperative that these criteria remain transparent to mitigate bias. The utilization of non-probability random sampling aligns with the purpose of this study which is to provide a descriptive exploration of the research subject, rather than to extrapolate findings to the broader population.

The approach employed for sampling and selecting respondents is characterized as purposive sampling, whereby respondents are chosen deliberately based on predefined criteria. In this instance, the criteria for respondents involve individuals engaged in online shopping within each marketplace: Blibli, Bukalapak, Lazada, Shopee, TikTok Shop, Tokopedia and Zalora. The cumulative count of respondents amounts to 442, however two responses did not meet the criteria, therefore only 440 data were being proceeded. Data collected spanning from June to July 2023.

This study employs an online questionnaire administered through a Google Form to gather data. There are seven Google Form for each marketplace and with the help of seven enumerators located in Jakarta and Bogor. The data collection methodology employs the snowballing technique, which entails the initial respondents sharing the online questionnaire with their respective contacts or relations.

Data Analysis

The collected data is transferred from Google Form, which contains an online questionnaire to Microsoft Excel. The data comprises two distinct sections for answering each research question. The initial segment pertains to data designated for neuromarketing analysis, which undergoes descriptive analysis utilizing Excel. The subsequent part concerns the assessment of customers' attitude dimensions towards online shopping. This evaluation is carried out through regression analyses facilitated by version 26.0 of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The regression analysis aims to identify which dimensions exhibit a statistically significant influence on customers' attitudes (partial analysis) for each marketplace and for the aggregate data.

HASIL DAN PEMBAHASAN

Respondent Characteristics

Total respondents that meet the criteria are 440 out of 442. Female respondent is 62,3% and male respondent is 37,7%. Shopee has the highest respondent (21,4%) and Zalora is the lowest only consists of 8,2% from the total respondents.

Table 5: Respondents' Profile

Marketplace	Respondent	Female	Male
Blibli	44	26	18
Bukalapak	43	32	11
Lazada	90	49	41
Shopee	94	64	32
TikTok Shop	84	47	37
Tokopedia	49	29	20
Zalora	36	27	9
Total	440	274	168

Source: Processed Data (2023)

Online Shopping Frequencies in the Marketplace

Respondents do online shopping 1 to 3 times per month is the majority with percentage 75,8%. The highest marketplace that has 1-3 x online shopping is TikTok Shop (83,3%) and the lowest is Bukalapak. The most frequent online shopping, which is more than 10 times a month is the customer of Zalora with the percentage of 13,9% whereas the lowest is Lazada.

Table 6: Online Shopping Frequencies per month

Marketplace	1-3x	4-10x	>10x
Blibli	33	5	6
Bukalapak	26	15	2
Lazada	73	16	1
Shopee	65	20	9
TiktokShop	70	11	3
Tokopedia	40	7	2
Zalora	26	5	5
Total	333	79	28

Source: Processed Data (2023)

Marketplace's Persona

Consumers' Persona can be comprehended by the most selection of lifestyle values from the Limbic Map of Hausel. All consumer in each marketplace in Indonesia are in Balance System with Family as the value in Limbic Map. Second choice of values in Dominance with Victory or Success as the value of Limbic Map, except for Zalora, i.e., Stimulant (the value is Fun). Trendyol which the biggest marketplace in Turkiye, the consumer is in the Adventure Thrill at Limbic Map (Kemora & Pasaribu, 2023).

Table 7: Consumers' Lifestyle values & Limbic Map of Hausel

Marketplace	Values	Limbic Map
Blibli	1. Family	Balance
	2. Victory	Dominance
Bukalapak	1. Family	Balance
	2. Victory	Dominance
Lazada	1. Family	Balance
	2. Victory	Dominance
Shopee	1. Family	Balance
	2. Victory	Dominance
TikTok Shop	1. Family	Balance
	2. Victory	Dominance
Tokopedia	1. Family	Balance
	2. Victory	Dominance
Zalora	1. Family	Balance
	2. Fun	Stimulant

Source: Processed Data (2023)

Consumer Limbic Type of all marketplaces in Indonesia is open-minded with the product feature that the most important when doing the decision on buying online is the quality of the product. The second feature of the product is family friendliness, which is the Harmonizer in Limbic Type of Hausel except for TikTok Shop Marketplace i.e., Hedonist with innovation as the product feature. Tokopedia has equally on features quality, innovation, and family

friendliness. Trendyol marketplace in Turkiye the type of limbic is adventurer where the feature is performance (Kemora & Pasaribu, 2023).

Table 8: The most importance of product feature and Limbic Type

Marketplace	Product Feature	Limbic Type
Blibli	1. Quality	Open-minded
	2. Family friendliness	Hamonizer
Bukalapak	1. Quality	Open-minded
	2. Family friendliness	Hamonizer
Lazada	1. Quality	Open-minded
	2. Family friendliness	Hamonizer
Shopee	1. Quality	Open-minded
	2. Family friendliness	Hamonizer
TiktokShop	1. Quality	Open-minded
	2. Inovation	Hedonist
Tokopedia	Quality/Inovation/	Open-minded/
	Family friendliness	Hedonist/Harmonizer
Zalora	1. Quality	Open-minded
	2. Family friendliness	Hamonizer

Source: Processed Data (2023)

The focus of advertising of marketplace perceived by consumers with the motive of quality is marketplace Blibli, Shopee, TikTok Shop, Tokopedia and Zalora. Quality motive is in Discipline Control on Limbic Map. Bukalapak and Lazada have Cordiality as the motive perceived by customers on their advertising. Cordiality motive is in the Fantasy/Pleasure in the Limbic Map. The second motive is Ease in the Fantasy/Pleasure in the Limbic Map for marketplace Blibli, Shopee, TikTok Shop, Tokopedia and Zalora. Bukalapak and Lazada's motive for the second is quality in the Discipline Control of Limbic Map.

Table 9: Marketplace Focus of Advertising and Limbic Map of Marketplace Perceived by Customer

Marketplace	Focus of Ad.	Limbic Map
Blibli	1. Quality	Discipline Control
	2. Ease	Fantasy/Pleasure
Bukalapak	1. Cordiality	Fantasy/Pleasure
	2. Quality	Discipline Control
Lazada	1. Cordiality	Fantasy/Pleasure
	2. Quality	Discipline Control
Shopee	1. Quality	Discipline Control
	2. Ease	Fantasy/Pleasure
TikTok Shop	1. Quality	Discipline Control
	2. Ease	Fantasy/Pleasure
Tokopedia	1. Quality	Discipline Control
	2. Ease	Fantasy/Pleasure
Zalora	1. Quality	Discipline Control
	2. Ease	Fantasy/Pleasure

Source: Processed Data (2023)

Based on the above results, it can be established that the persona of marketplace brand. All the marketplace in Indonesia has the similarities values, features, and motives which are in the Limbic Map of Balance System (Figure 3). As for the Limbic Map, because of the brand of marketplace in Balance System, therefore the type of Limbic is Harmonizer.

Figure 3: Seven Marketplace Persona of Limbic Map Perceived by Customers

Online Consumers' Preference

The model for linear regression with dependent variable is the attitude of customers in online shopping with each marketplace. All marketplaces have the F test accepted or all the variables Persona dan Brand Identity simultaneously give significant effect on consumers' attitudes for each marketplace (sig, value for Anova for F test < 0,05). It is also said that all models for each marketplace and the aggregate data are accepted to be good models. Table 10 shows the value of R square and the significance of coefficient on each marketplace. The highest R square is Bukalapak 92, 8% and the lowest is Zalora 65, 4%. From partial test of t test, the significant coefficient, each marketplace has different results. The consumers' preference for marketplace Blibli is Domain Name (X7). The brand identity of Bukalapak that has significant effect on consumer's attitude on online shopping is Information Quality (X2), Design (X4) and Entertainment (X5). Marketplace Lazada's Persona has significant effect on consumer preference on online shopping with other Brand Identity: Design (X4), Entertainment (X5) and Domain Name (X7). Persona of Shopee also affect the attitude of consumers in buying online, together with Personalization (X6) and Domain Name (X7). Marketplace TikTok Shop the only brand identity that influences consumers' attitude is Entertainment (X5). Tokopedia brand identity that gives significant effect is Usability (X3), Personalization (X6) and Domain Name (X7). Zalora has an interesting result where there is no partial coefficient that has significant effect towards consumers' preference. It can be summarized that only two marketplaces that Pesona gives significant effect on consumers' preference on buying online, which are Lazada and Shopee. The aggregate data of all seven marketplaces shows that R square is 83,4% and it is proven that Persona has significantly influenced the consumers' preferences on online shopping. Other dimensions that are accepted include Design (X4), Entertainment (X5), Personalization (X6) and Domain Name (X7).

Table 10: Linear Regression of Consumers' Preferences on Marketplaces

Marketplace	R_squar e (%)	Anova (F_sig)	Coefficient (t_sig)
Blibli	78,3	0,00	X7
Bukalapak	92,8	0,00	X2, X4, X5
Lazada	88,4	0,00	Persona, X4, X5, X7
Shopee	75,1	0,00	Persona, X6, X7
TiktokShop	80,1	0,00	X5
Tokopedia	83,7	0,00	X3, X6, X7
Zalora	65,4	0,00	-
Total	83,4	0,00	Persona, X4, X5, X6, X7

Source: Processed Data (2023)

For more details, Table 11 shows the results of of t-test for the aggregate data for all marketplaces. The strongest influence is coming from Domain Name (X7) with the value of 0,314, subsequently Personalization (X6) 0,240, Design (X4) 0,215, Entertainment (X5) 0,184,

and the smallest effect is from Persona 0,082. The brand identity that does not have a significant impact is Interactivity (X1), Information Quality (X2) and Usability (X3). Furthermore, the nexus of Information Quality and the consumers' attitude on buying online has negative relation. This aspect of information quality relates to how customers perceive the quantity, quality, and abundance of information provided on the marketplace. It also includes the way the information is organized and presented.

Table 11: t-test of Brand Identity Consumer Attitudes on Online Shopping at Marketplace

	Unstan. Coef. B	Std. Error	Stan. Coef. Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	-1.229	1.174		-1.047	0.296
Persona	0.082	0.024	0.082	3.442	0.001
X1	0.018	0.099	0.006	0.186	0.853
X2	-0.092	0.118	-0.029	-0.780	0.436
X3	0.020	0.160	0.005	0.124	0.901
X4	0.709	0.146	0.215	4.868	0.000
X5	0.751	0.157	0.184	4.786	0.000
X6	0.764	0.136	0.240	5.637	0.000
X7	1.008	0.141	0.314	7.146	0.000
Dependent Variable: Y					

Source: Processed Data (2023)

The equation of consumers' attitudes on online shopping can be written as follows:

$$Y = -1.229 + 0.082\text{Persona} + 0.018\text{X1} - 0.092\text{X2} + 0.020\text{X3} + 0.709\text{X4} + 0.751\text{X5} + 0.764\text{X6} + 1.008\text{X7}$$

DISCUSSION

Persona

Brand personality or Persona based on neuromarketing will harness the goal of business in particular for MSMEs which is buying decision (Toldos-Romero & Orozco-Gómez, 2015). The values and the product features that are important for customers can give consumer insight of each marketplace of the persona of buyer. The most important value of lifestyle for consumers shows that all marketplaces are the same, which is Quality or in the Limbic Map categories in Balance System. The second is Victory or success that is in the Dominance System. It can be

concluded that family is the center of attention for consumers' attitude for buying online in Indonesia. By exploring the neural mechanisms that underlie consumer reactions, neuromarketing aims to furnish marketers with valuable perspectives, enabling the formulation of marketing campaigns that are not only more efficient but also more lucrative. This, in turn, propels businesses towards heightened accomplishments within the competitive market arena (Alsharif et al., 2021). Players of MSMEs can monetize the consumers' persona using the Family center value and promising victory (Baldo et al., 2022). Furthermore, studies in the field of neuromarketing have demonstrated that emotions' valence and levels of arousal have a significant influence on the way individuals perceive trust, express intentions to share, and engage with brands on social media platforms and also marketplace (Bigne et al., 2021; Kakaria et al., 2023). Digital marketing such as short video or user generated content (UGC) should touch the value of Family, Victory and the Limbic Type which is Open-Minded and Harmonizer. The utilization of visual aesthetics on value of family and feature of product about quality, the incorporation of simplicity, and the facilitation of sensory engagement within social media materials have been empirically shown to amplify consumer focus and emotional reactions (Baldo et al., 2022) as well as in marketplace platform. Consequently, these elements play a pivotal role in shaping brand credibility and stimulating inclinations to share such content.

According to Cui et al. (2019) brand personality exerts a notable and affirmative impact on users' perceived value, underscoring the existence of distinct brand attributes and competitors within the short video industry. This phenomenon allows consumers to identify value congruent with their preferences during the perceptual value assessment process. Brand Personality or Persona can be perceived by customers in the form of advertisement of marketplace. The seven marketplaces are using motives of Quality, Cordiality and Ease. These motives of advertisement perceived by customers are congruent with the customers' lifestyle values and important features of product. Therefore, the results are empirically proven the theory of "Similarity-Attraction" (Aaker, 1997; Xu et al., 2023). It can be summarized that the persona of seven marketplace Blibli, Bukalapak, Lazada, Shopee, TikTok Shop, Tokopedia and Zalora are all in Balance System according to Hausel with the Limbic Type is Open-minded and Harmonizer. Persona for marketplace in Turkiye has different results, Trendyol has Fantasy/Pleasure for Limbic Map and Open-minded and Hedonist for Limbic Map (Kemora & Pasaribu, 2023). Research in Mongolia found that the Limbic Type of consumers are Harmonizer and Traditionalist (G, 2018).

Consumers' Preferences

Blibli

Blibli is one of Indonesia's emerging online marketplaces, as evidenced by data from the first quarter of 2023, Blibli ranks forth as a marketplace with the highest number of visitors in Indonesia the monthly visitor count for Blibli reached 24,3 million with month-on-month (mom) growth 5% (Azkiya, 2023). From this figure, it can be said that since the birth of Blibli in 2011, this marketplace has delved in the mind of consumers. The domain name represents the brand image with blibli.com as its logo (Figure 4). Study on marketplace Blibli showed that

brand image as a proxy to domain name has a significant impact on the buying decisions (Liliana, 2023). However, this research presents contrasting findings, as quality information exhibits a noteworthy influence on consumer preferences on marketplace Blibli (Alpian & Nurlinda, 2023).

Figure 4: Blibli logo and domain name

Bukalapak

Information Quality and Design of Bukalapak gave the significant effect towards the attitude of consumers that congruent with the study done by (Adellia & Prasetio, 2016). The positive and significant effect of the entertainment factor provided by Bukalapak on consumer attitudes is consistent with consumers' overall satisfaction (Suthianto & Syah, 2023). Moreover, the design of a Bukalapak's website exerts a positive and substantial impact on purchase decisions (Mulyana et al., 2020). These results underscore the significance of enhancing visual presentation tactics to attract consumers' attention and establish emotionally gratifying interactions, particularly within the realm of social media marketing (Kakaria et al., 2023) as well as in marketplace.

Lazada

Research endeavors have been delving into the evaluation of brand personality or Persona through the utilization of neuroscientific approaches. The results revealed that brand personality does indeed exert an influence on purchase intentions in the context of online shopping (Xu et al., 2023). The result of Lazada has proven that Persona affects consumers preferences. Personalization and Entertainment factors in Lazada also gave significant effect on consumers' attitudes supported by other studies (Kollmann & Suckow, 2012; Suthianto & Syah, 2023). Study done by Baskara & Sukaatmadja (2016) revealed that online trust and perceived enjoyment, as a proxy for entertainment, both exhibit a positive and noteworthy association with online shopping satisfaction, repurchase intention of Lazada Indonesia consumers. As for Domain Name factor, Lazada from the SWOT analysis. Stands out as one of the most prosperous businesses due to its capability to generate the utmost value for customers and sustain it over time. Moreover, the study found that one of the strength of Lazada is extremely straightforward to locate using search engines (Amanah & Harahap, 2020). From the statistic of the first quartile 2023, the growth of Lazada visitor m-o-m is the highest among marketplace in Indonesia which is 13% (Azkiya, 2023). It is indicated that Persona, Personalization and Entertainment of Lazada's brand identity affect its consumers' attitude.

Shopee

During the period of January-March this year, the Shopee website garnered an average of 157.9 million visits per month as the highest visitor, far surpassing its competitors and the growth momentum is 10% in the first quartile 2023 (Azkiya, 2023) as the factors of Persona, Personalization and Entertainment factor contributed to. According to the findings of other research, the Brand Personality of Shopee Indonesia, as per Aaker's theory (Aaker, 1997), has a notable impact on the intention to use the platform (Agrippina & Suratnoaji, 2022). Shopee, with the support of artificial intelligence or AI technologies, have ushered in a significantly personalized experience for customers on Shopee. This has enhanced the enjoyment and distinctiveness of online shopping, all the while empowering brands and sellers to boost their traffic and expansion. For instance, buyers can utilize filters integrated into the search engine, leading them to a search page populated with more pertinent items, spanning categories, sellers' locations, and price ranges. Furthermore, Shopee employs deep learning to offer customers more accurate suggestions based on their prior searches or purchases. Utilizing AI, Shopee Feed is constructed using users' following lists, search histories, and order histories, culminating in a tailored homepage that seamlessly aligns with their preferences and interests (Hue et al., 2022).

TikTok Shop

The TikTok Shop stands out among e-commerce platforms due to its innovative approach, allowing users to seamlessly integrate social media engagement with purchasing and sales within the same application. Customers are drawn to online shopping on the TikTok Shop platform because of its distinctive features, notably the live streaming program on the TikTok Shop website, which is perceived as entertainment, that serves as the primary driver for customers to directly engage in shopping through TikTok Shop. TikTok possesses the potential to enhance the reputation of a company or a product, leveraging viral marketing and word-of-mouth advertising. This is evident in the TikTok Shop feature, which provides users with an e-commerce avenue for conducting online purchases, showcasing its role in achieving this effect (Anwar & Rizkiyah Hasbi, 2023). Moreover, it offers a wide range of entertainment through short user-generated videos or UGC, serving as a valuable source for discovering intriguing locations, food, and various items of interest. The TikTok algorithm is user-friendly, fostering a space where individuals can refine their creative abilities (Rachmad, 2022) and fulfilling the entertainment need for the customers.

Tokopedia

Usability, Personalization and Domain Name of Tokopedia brand identities give significant impact on consumers' preferences as can be seen in the statistics of the number of visitors in the first quartile, the Tokopedia website achieved an average of 117 million visits every month (Azkiya, 2023). Usability factor conforms with other research findings, it is stated that all of the heuristic methods have a severity rating of 1 (one), which signifies that errors or deficiencies can be tolerated by users. In other words, the usability issues present on the Tokopedia website are not a concern for users and are considered to not disrupt users when

accessing the Tokopedia website (Aziza, 2019). Intelligent personalization aims to generate favorable encounters and provide pleasurable values within electronic marketplaces like in Tokopedia (Puspitasari et al., 2023). Domain Name has significant effect on consumers' attitudes as in conformity with research by Muna et al. (2022) where drawing from its analysis utilizing Google Lighthouse on the Tokopedia e-marketplace, encompassing four key metrics: Performance, Accessibility, Best Practices, and SEO, it can be deduced that Tokopedia outperforms in multiple dimensions of the evaluated metrics. Tokopedia has effectively implemented a plethora of optimization enhancements, and these findings are poised to have a substantial impact on the overall operational performance of the marketplace.

Zalora

Zalora is renowned as a marketplace catering to the luxury segment of products. The Zalora brand has become synonymous with a platform for luxurious and sophisticated items, setting it apart from mass-product marketplaces. Consequently, the need for brand identity differentiation from other marketplaces is not necessary. This indication supports the research outcome that, in partial regression results, there are no factors significantly influencing consumer preferences towards Zalora. Other studies also mirror this similarity, where Brand Satisfaction with Zalora significantly impacts Brand Loyalty, and Luxury Brand Attachment significantly influences Brand Loyalty (BRIGITTA, 2022). This affirms that Zalora has already established a strong brand identity as a marketplace for luxury items.

SIMPULAN

The practical implications arising from this study have the potential to greatly enhance the effectiveness of digital marketing strategies for MSMEs. Through the Persona of each marketplace and it has its own consumers' preferences, businesses and marketers can formulate campaigns and ads in the light of similarity – attraction to win the heart, mind and “money” of customers. These findings can be utilized to fine-tune digital marketing strategies and craft content that proves more successful in capturing attention and engaging potential customers. Furthermore, MSMEs can utilize each marketplace's Persona by the values of motives in the interaction with users/customers.

The implication of the research is that the research supports the theory of similarity – attraction. However, the concept of a 'similarity-attraction' effect between brand and consumer personalities is contentious. Some research studies provide support for this attraction mechanism, while others have discovered that there isn't always alignment between brand and consumer personalities. Despite extensive exploration of the validity of the self-congruence theory, there's a lack of empirical investigation into whether a significant relationship exists between consumer personality and brand personality. This research will contribute to providing reasoning that empirically demonstrates how brand personality or persona influences consumer preferences.

In terms of scientific methodology, several key considerations warrant attention in this study. Firstly, the use of a non-probability purposive sampling technique raises concerns about the extent to which the findings can be generalized to a wider population. The resulting sample size may inadequately capture the diverse spectrum of online customers in Indonesia, thereby potentially introducing biases into the outcomes. Secondly, the adoption of an online questionnaire for data collection introduces the possibility of response bias, where participants might furnish inaccurate or socially desirable answers, thus compromising result validity. Lastly, the reliance on self-reported data exposes the research to potential recall bias or misinterpretation, as participants' ability to accurately recollect their online shopping behaviors and preferences could be compromised.

For future research endeavors, it is advisable to employ a diversified approach to sampling techniques, encompassing a blend of probability-based methods, to attain a more comprehensive and representative cross-section of online customers in Indonesia, thereby bolstering the potential for broader applicability of the results. Additionally, adopting a mixed-methods strategy could prove beneficial by complementing self-reported data with advanced technologies of neuroscience like eye-tracking, allowing for a more direct observation and understanding of consumer preferences within the online marketplace environment

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